

Components Required for Human-Centred AI

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Abstract. Artificial intelligence holds many benefits but can also cause harm when not following a human-centred approach. This approach is called human-centred AI (HCAI) and aims to augment human abilities to create safe, reliable and trustworthy solutions. A systematic literature review was used as a research approach to identify the components of HCAI. Thirty-two papers were analysed as part of the study using thematic analysis. Twenty-four themes were identified, namely agile, auditable, available, comprehensible, controllable, dependable, directable, explainable, fair, interpretable, observable, predictable, privacy, reliable, resilient, robust, safe, secure, traceable, trackable, transparent, trustworthy, unbiased, and usable. Ethics, fairness, governance, privacy, safety, security, reliability, explainability, transparency, and trustworthiness were the more apparent themes. The identified components can be utilised in developing AI solutions from a human-centred perspective. Including the components in a development approach should assist in developing ethical, fair, secure, reliable, understandable, trustworthy, and safe AI solutions while ensuring human and ethical impacts are considered.

Keywords: Human-centred, artificial intelligence, HCAI, augment human abilities.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to tasks typically executed by humans being performed by computers [1]. It utilises algorithms like machine learning (ML), neural networks, and deep learning [1, 2]. The presence of AI in the daily lives of humans increases continually and influences daily activities [1, 3-6].

AI solutions are data-driven and learn independently to achieve the best results for the set goal, but they do not typically consider the human or ethical impact [3, 7]. The inclusion of AI into systems can harm humans through, for example, bias and security breaches [2, 5, 8, 9]. Users and stakeholders are not typically included in developing AI solutions [10]. The technical nature of AI is an obstacle to including non-technical individuals in the development process [10]. The increased presence of AI and its problems has given rise to human-centred AI (HCAI) [1, 4].

HCAI aims to aid humans by considering human input and feedback while considering human rights, safety, fairness, and dignity to enhance human competencies,

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imagination, efficiency, and confidence [2, 4, 11-14]. The HCAI approach differs from AI in its development process and the product delivered as output [11]. AI focuses on process autonomy and algorithm efficiency, whereas humans have become essential in HCAI [5, 11, 14, 15]. HCAI delivers products that support, strengthen, enable, and enhance human abilities and efficiencies [5, 6, 11]. HCAI does not aim to replace humans but rather to augment human capabilities by involving humans in the development process, thereby providing humans control over AI [4, 11, 13, 16]. In addition, having a more human-centred approach to developing AI systems would improve AI system adoption, allowing AI systems to exert a more significant impact on delivering human needs [2, 11, 15].

Therefore, the main research question of this paper is: *What are the components required for a human-centred approach for (sic) the development of systems that use artificial intelligence?* As delineated by the research question, the scope of the study encompassed identifying the key components promoting human-centredness in AI from the literature. The scope excludes investigating AI regulatory frameworks, standards, explainability methods or proposing a new methodological approach. Instead, the study aims to integrate existing knowledge to enhance the understanding of human-centred components highlighted in the existing literature. This study forms part of a larger, overarching study.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents the research approach, Section 3 contains the data analysis, Section 4 discusses the results and findings of the literature review, and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Background

Schleith, Norkute [15] describe AI as a process that uses data to perform a task resembling human action, intending to elicit an outcome. In addition, AI fits the description of technologies imitating human thinking to improve complex processes and decision-making [12, 17]. AI strives to enable machines to execute human intelligence-related tasks, like learning, generalisation, problem-solving, interpretation, and statistics [8, 12, 18].

HCAI refers to developing AI algorithms through a human-centred development approach [2, 5, 11]. HCAI focuses on users at the centre of design and development [2, 4, 5, 14, 15]. The process considers user requirements and measures user efficiency and happiness [5, 14]. The main goal of HCAI is to allow for a significant amount of human control and automation, whereby humans can influence decisions and events [2, 4, 11, 12, 14, 19]. To that end, a balance must be found between efficiency, automation and humanity [4, 20].

HCAI solutions are achieved when designers, software developers, and management involve different stakeholders in their design and development [2, 14]. User involvement is essential to delivering a solution that would meet user needs and highlight the limitations of AI systems and the need for a human-centred approach [4, 11, 15, 16, 20]. Reliable human-centred AI solutions are achieved through trustworthy technical practices that depict human obligation [14].

3 Research Approach

This paper aims to understand the components required for a human-centred approach to developing AI solutions, using a literature review to understand the scope of HCAI. A literature review is the process of reading and evaluating literature to gain an understanding of the content and context and seek support for a research study [21, 22]. A sound literature review should follow a thorough step-by-step process to integrate peer-reviewed literature into a whole to provide support for the research problem in question [23-25]. Rouhani, Mahrin [26] suggest a three-step process for a systematic literature review: (1) planning, (2) execution, and (3) result analysis. The planning step entails determining the research questions, secondary questions, and scope of the study [26]. The execution step entails finding relevant literature based on keywords and explaining how literature was evaluated by defining inclusion and exclusion criteria [26]. The result analysis step entails reporting the study results by comparing and linking literature from different authors to provide new insights into the field of study [26].

As part of the second step, execution, the author executed a keyword search for “Human-centred AI” in *Scopus* for reviewed articles published between 2020 and 2024. Ben Schneiderman [27] presented the term HCAI in 2019, which industry and researchers had generally embraced by 2020. Only open-access reviewed articles and books were included; commentary, notes, and lecture notes were excluded. The included articles had to have been cited at least once. Only articles from the following databases were considered: *ACM Digital*, *IEEE Xplore*, *ScienceDirect*, *SpringerLink*, *Taylor & Francis*, and *Emerald* (**Table 1**). These databases are a source of high-quality peer-reviewed articles.

Table 1. Total number of papers and books

Database	Total	Included	Excluded
ACM Digital Library	20	13	7
IEEE Xplore	8	5	3
ScienceDirect	15	8	7
SpringerLink	6	2	4
Taylor & Francis	4	2	2
Emerald Insight	1	1	0
Oxford (Book)	1	1	0
Total	55	32	23

One hundred and ninety-four (194) articles emerged in the initial search using the search keyword for 2020 to 2024. Only the 55 articles from the databases listed in **Table 1** were reviewed. Twenty-three (23) articles were excluded due to relevancy or duplication. The remaining 32 articles were coded and themed.

Fig. 1. Components of HCAI: Network Graph

The pink circles (nodes) indicate the main topic identified by *InfraNodus*. The measure of betweenness centrality (BC) determines the size of the circle; hence, the higher the BC measure, the bigger the circle. The green lines represent the interrelationships between topics, whereby the closer the connection, the higher the weight of the connection.

5 Discussion of results

5.1 Components of Human-Centred AI

Shneiderman [11] lists twenty-five components in the literature contributing to human-centeredness in AI systems, as shown in **Table 2**. The most critical are reliability, safety, and trustworthiness [11], all of which are essential aspects of achieving ethical AI that ensures data governance [4, 11].

Table 2. Components of HCAI [11]

Component	Reference
Agile	[11]
Auditable	[9, 11, 14]
Available	[4, 11]
Comprehensible	[1, 3, 6, 7, 11, 16, 29]
Controllable	[2, 4, 6, 11, 30]
Dependable	[11]
Directable	[11]
Explainable	[2, 5, 9, 11, 16, 18, 31-35]
Fair	[2-4, 9, 11, 18-20, 29, 36, 37]
Interpretable	[2, 6, 9, 11, 16, 20]
Observable	[11]
Predictable	[1, 11, 16]
Privacy	[4, 5, 11, 17]
Reliable	[2, 4, 6, 11, 17, 18]
Resilient	[11]
Robust	[9, 11]
Safe	[4, 6, 9, 11, 17]
Secure	[11, 17]
Traceable	[11]
Trackable	[11]
Transparent	[1-4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 18, 20, 32, 34, 35, 37, 38]
Trustworthy	[2, 4-6, 11, 16-19, 30, 34, 37]
Unbiased	[2, 4, 9, 11, 14, 16, 19, 39]
Usable	[2, 6, 11, 16]

It is difficult to evaluate the impact of changes in the development process on these components [11].

5.2 Human-Centred AI

HCAI is the development of AI algorithms with a human-centred development approach [2, 5, 11]. HCAI aims to aid humans by considering human input and feedback while considering human rights, safety, fairness, and dignity to enhance human competencies, imagination, efficiency, and confidence [2, 4, 11-14]. For this study, the definition utilised for HCAI is that HCAI is a method for establishing human control over AI solutions and associating AI solutions with human, ethical, and legal standards to deliver reliable, safe, and trustworthy AI solutions [6].

The HCAI approach differs from AI in the development process it follows and the product it delivers as output [11]. In addition, the aspects deemed necessary at the time of development differ between HCAI and AI [11]. AI focuses on process autonomy and algorithm efficiency, whereas humans have become essential in HCAI [5, 11, 14, 15]. HCAI delivers products that support, strengthen, enable, and boost human abilities and efficiencies [5, 6, 11].

HCAI focuses on the users, placing them at the centre during design and development [2, 4, 5, 14, 15]. As such, user requirements are considered, and user efficiency and happiness are measured [5, 14]. HCAI mainly strives to allow for a significant amount of human control and automation, whereby humans can influence decisions and events [2, 4, 11, 12, 14, 19]. Hence, a balance must be found between efficiency, automation and humanity [4, 20]. In addition, the user interface should be user-friendly and pleasurable to use [3, 19].

HCAI solutions are achieved when designers, software developers, and management involve different stakeholders in the design and development [2, 14]. Human-computer interaction (HCI) principles are also incorporated into the design and development process [2-4, 12, 15].

The HCAI approach advocates for cooperative symbiosis between humans and AI, whereby users and stakeholders are included in design and development [2, 4, 12, 16]. The two main features of HCAI are systems that comprehend humans and human trust in these systems [2].

AI should improve and aid human capabilities to facilitate productivity and success [1, 2, 6, 17]. The aim should not be to replace humans, as AI cannot recreate human intelligence and insight [2, 6, 11, 17]. Humans can think logically, have discussions, make intelligent decisions, and execute physical and intellectual tasks without calculations [17]. Developing truly human-centred AI requires an understanding of human reasoning, behaviour, and skills [6, 40].

5.3 Discussion of main components

5.3.1 Ethics, fairness, and governance

The unethical use of AI poses substantial risks [9, 17]. AI is created using ML, which is statistical and can thus lead to discrimination if certain groups of people are clustered

together, and that group is impacted more positively or negatively as a consequence of such classification [4, 10, 19]. The quality of data being used by the ML is another risk factor [3, 9, 20]; AI relies on a significant amount of data, and the quality of the data determines the quality of the results [3, 9]. Data can be biased when using a skewed dataset as training data, which, in turn, can influence subsequent AI results and decision-making [3, 4, 9, 19, 20].

AI mainly focuses on generating revenue without considering how humans might benefit [9, 11]. A shift needs to occur from generating only profit to practices enabling ethical AI [9, 11]. The human-centred approach is a well-stated practice that requires a system to operate ethically [2, 9, 10]. Ethical AI aims to leverage the benefits of these technologies while aligning the design with regulations, human rights, values, and standards [3, 4, 17].

Ethics in AI and the speed at which AI develops is concerning [1, 17]. These ethical concerns are related to humanity, bias, fairness, disinformation, lack of transparency, safety, inaccuracies, confidentiality, and employment [4, 9, 17, 19]. These ethical concerns must be addressed in each phase of the system development lifecycle [9, 11]. The involvement of stakeholders in the design and development of AI systems ensures the mitigation of bias results [2, 4, 9]. The stakeholders involved in the design and development influence ethical views and fairness that are considered and embedded into an AI system [4, 9, 19]. Ethics is essential to HCAI [11, 17]. AI4People suggests an ethical framework that includes goodness, integrity, and accuracy [5]. Bingley, Curtis [5] point to the ethical AI principles per Microsoft: “fairness, inclusiveness, reliability, safety, transparency, privacy, security, and accountability”.

Nakao, Strappelli [19] explain fairness as freedom and justice, whereby people have identical opportunities and rights. AI systems are based on the developers' views, which can lead to bias. Therefore, it is imperative to include other stakeholders' views to enable fairness [3, 4, 9, 10, 19]. These systems should extend their focus beyond statistical fairness and consider future use of the system and its impact on humans [3, 20, 36, 37]. Fairness is also measured by the extent to which it adheres to social standards and values [19, 36, 37]; accordingly, fairness must be applied on an individual and group basis, where the individual and the group to which individuals belong are treated fairly [19, 29].

5.3.2 Privacy, safety, and security

AI systems raise privacy, safety, and security concerns and may experience external attacks [4, 9, 17]. Data privacy and safeguarding personal data should be considered in designing and developing AI systems [4, 17]. According to Alfredo, Echeverria [4], data privacy is safeguarding and managing personal and proprietary information. System security also protects against malicious code, failure, loss of control, and theft of personal data [17]. In addition, organisations must ensure they know what data may be shared without violating privacy [4].

User trust is established through the perception of data protection [4]. This perception is enabled by robust data privacy standards and precise, honest data collection methods [4].

5.3.3 Reliability

According to Shneiderman [11], AI solutions are reliable when they deliver the anticipated results and sound technical principles are applied in their design and development. Alfredo, Echeverria [4] explains reliability as an AI solution providing the correct information the user expects and when it performs consistently. Reliability can be achieved by comparing data sources, implementing audit trails, testing, and implementing privacy, safety, and security measures [4, 11].

5.3.4 Explainability and transparency

Explainability refers to the ability to generate and present understandable explanations of complex AI models to users to enable the visibility of the system processes [16, 18, 31-34, 38]. Explainability is vital for creating responsible AI [9, 18, 33, 34] and a means to create transparency and accountability in AI solutions and their evaluation [9, 18, 32-35].

Transparency is imperative for AI solutions and assists in building trust [3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 18, 32, 35, 37, 38]; the principle relates to storing and managing data openly and understandably [4, 38]. Openness extends to explaining in an understandable way how decisions are made [3, 7, 18, 38]. Transparency is required to facilitate understanding, which enables evaluation of the AI system regarding changes and improvements [32, 34, 35]. According to Schmitt, Csomor [35], the AI Act requires human oversight and clear explanations of the system for transparency. Users should be able to audit the decision-making of AI solutions and interpret the data to ensure that the outcome aligns with their expectations [2].

5.3.5 Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is a primary concern in AI systems and should be planned for in the design phase [4, 17]. Alfredo, Echeverria [4] list three components of trustworthiness, namely trust, transparency, and accountability. Bingley, Curtis [5] state that the European Union lists seven fundamental stipulations for AI solutions to be deemed trustworthy, with transparency, accountability, and consideration of societal and environmental norms as the main requirements. Accountability can be explained as accepting liability for decisions and the outcomes of such decisions [4, 9, 18].

Trust is influenced by humans having to surrender control and decision-making to automated systems [30]. Therefore, AI systems must be trustworthy for humans to adopt them [3, 17, 34]. Trust is only achieved when an AI system performs its primary function safely and reliably [4, 17]. In addition, trust can be facilitated through transparency and explainability [2, 4, 16, 37]. Rong, Leemann [16] explain trust in an AI system as the amalgamation of users' assurance of its precision, its level of grasping and usability, and the level of decision-making the user accepts.

6 Conclusion

HCAI is the development of AI algorithms with a human-centred development approach [2, 5, 11], for which this article aims to identify the requisite components.

The authors utilised a systematic literature review as a research approach to identify the components of HCAI. Thirty-two papers were analysed as part of the study using thematic analysis, from which twenty-four themes were identified: agile, auditable, available, comprehensible, controllable, dependable, directable, explainable, fair, interpretable, observable, predictable, privacy, reliable, resilient, robust, safe, secure, traceable, trackable, transparent, trustworthy, unbiased, and usable. Ethics, fairness, governance, privacy, safety, security, reliability, explainability, transparency, and trustworthiness were more apparent themes.

The identified components have practical significance in their utilisation for developing AI solutions from a human-centred perspective. Including the components above in a design approach would assist in developing AI solutions with the following characteristics: ethical, fair, secure, reliable, understandable, trustworthy, and safe while considering the human and ethical impact and delivering AI solutions that aid humans.

Furthermore, the identified components contribute theoretically to a larger, overarching study aimed at developing a human-centred framework for the development and evaluation of online systems that apply artificial intelligence. The larger study aims to develop a human-centred framework to guide the development and evaluation of AI solutions.

This study was limited to identifying and analysing the vital components in existing literature that encourage human-centredness in AI. The scope was limited to AI solutions developed for integration with online systems. The study did not perform empirical testing or evaluation of AI systems. Lastly, the study focused on general principles of human-centred design rather than domain-specific applications.

Future research might investigate how these components could be included in a formal development approach to ensure that AI is developed in a human-centred manner that ensures it is not biased, benefits humans, augments human abilities and is ethical, transparent, reliable, trustworthy, and explainable.

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